

Figure S1: Genotyping results of the *N. benthamiana* transformed lines with the CGEM targeting *XT1* locus.

a) Genotyping of LbCas12a CGEM lines.

20/37 = 54% mutated
12/20 = 60% biallelic

b) Genotyping of AsCas12a CGEM lines.

0 mutated lines